

An Intelligent Network Fuzzer for Protocol Testing in Healthcare Systems

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Abstract. Testing the robustness and security of network protocol implementations is essential across all domains. We present NETWORKFUZZER, a generic, feedback-driven network fuzzer designed to test and analyze protocol implementations by operating directly on real traffic. Unlike traditional code coverage-based fuzzers, NETWORKFUZZER works at the network level and employs a closed-loop fuzzing mechanism that dynamically adapts based on server responses. The system incorporates three key components: (i) response-aware fuzzing operators that perform protocol-specific packet mutations, (ii) a Conditional Tabular GAN (CT-GAN) model that learns from both normal and abnormal traffic to generate diverse and protocol-compliant test cases, and (iii) Large Language Models (LLMs) that automate the generation of testing rules from protocol specifications. While NETWORKFUZZER is protocol-agnostic and applicable to a wide range of network protocols, in this paper we focus on its application to the Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) protocol, which is commonly used for medical image exchange, to demonstrate its utility in healthcare cybersecurity. Our evaluation shows that NETWORKFUZZER effectively executes real-world attacks and generates realistic synthetic traffic, thus enhancing the robustness of testing and training for security systems.

Keywords: Network Fuzzing, Traffic Engineering, Attack Injection, GAN, LLM, DICOM Protocol Testing, Synthetic Traffic

1 Introduction

Context. Medical imaging is a cornerstone of modern healthcare, essential for accurate diagnosis, treatment planning, and patient management. The DICOM protocol serves as the global standard for the exchange, storage, and retrieval of medical images and related data [8]. By enabling interoperability among diverse medical imaging devices and systems, DICOM ensures that healthcare providers can efficiently access and interpret imaging data, regardless of the vendor or institution. Central to the DICOM ecosystem is the Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS), which facilitates the secure storage, retrieval, and distribution of medical images and associated information. Even though PACS is not directly connected to the internet, it can still be vulnerable via internal networks. Exposed PACS servers face significant risks, such as network intrusions,

denial-of-service attacks, and other threats that compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of medical images [13,24].

Recent years have revealed critical vulnerabilities within DICOM systems, exposing them to potential cyberattacks [1,3,12]. These vulnerabilities threaten both the confidentiality of sensitive patient data and the integrity of medical images, which are vital for clinical decision-making. For instance, in 2017, researchers from Massachusetts General Hospital discovered thousands of unprotected DICOM servers worldwide, including hundreds in the United States, leaving patient information vulnerable to unauthorized access [12]. These incidents highlight the alarming consequences of inadequate security measures in DICOM implementations. Given the critical role of DICOM in healthcare and its growing exposure to sophisticated cyber threats, this underscores the importance of adopting advanced solutions, such as smart network fuzzers, to systematically probe DICOM systems for flaws.

Challenges. Several studies have been conducted on the detection and prediction of cyberattacks in stateful protocols [11,16] and in DICOM server implementation, such as the DCMTK library [23]. There is a lack of open-source solutions that enable the manual creation or editing of existing DICOM network protocol packets and their injection into a network, allowing researchers and practitioners to easily test proposed detection schemes. Tools like TCPREPLAY, SCAPY, and others have been employed for network testing, but they exhibit limitations when applied to the DICOM protocol. An open-source tool, 5GREPLAY, was recently introduced to forward network packets - unmodified or with basic modifications - between network interface cards (NICs) to trigger abnormal behaviors, provides an effective solution to fuzz testing 5G network [21] and HTTP/2 [10], extending this tool to test new protocols is not straightforward. Although, this tool has some limitations, as detailed below:

- C1 Lack of context-awareness.** 5GREPLAY does not account for the server’s responses after injecting packets, resulting in a lack of context-awareness that could otherwise improve the precision and effectiveness of the injections. DICOM is a stateful protocol where interactions between the client and server involve specific sequences and negotiations (e.g., A-ASSOCIATE and P-DATA). Without dynamically analyzing server responses, critical insights are missed, limiting the accuracy of the tests. Furthermore, 5GREPLAY supports only a limited set of basic atomic operations, such as deleting or duplicating packets and modifying attributes [21]. It lacks critical capabilities, such as reordering packets or dynamically adjusting attributes based on server feedback, which are essential for comprehensive protocol testing.
- C2 Lack of intelligent fuzzing mechanisms.** The absence of AI mechanisms in 5GREPLAY limits its ability to adapt to dynamic and complex protocol behaviors. Modern protocols like DICOM involve hierarchical data structures and stateful communications that require sophisticated and intelligent fuzzing strategies to uncover vulnerabilities. Incorporating AI, such as a GAN-based smart fuzzer, can enable the automated generation of diverse and realistic malformed packets.

C3 **Manually crafting test rules.** Manually crafting test rules for protocol validation is a time-intensive and error-prone process, particularly for complex protocols like DICOM, which include intricate attribute hierarchies, nested data structures, and strict communication sequences. The reliance on manual rule generation limits scalability and introduces potential human biases and oversights.

Proposal. In this paper, we introduce NETWORKFUZZER, a smart fuzzer for network traffic protocol, with a focus on the DICOM protocol. Unlike existing coverage-based fuzzers that rely on code coverage to generate new inputs for testing server binary executables [7,9,17,20], our smart fuzzer is designed to test the network functionalities of the DICOM protocol with respect to its specifications. The core idea is to alter network packets either online or offline in a highly flexible manner, inject them into the server, and adapt the modification process based on the server’s responses, thereby creating an efficient *closed-loop fuzzing* mechanism. To address the challenges mentioned above, we design and build NETWORKFUZZER on top of 5GREPLAY with following extensions: (i) takes into account server’s responses for an efficient fuzzing closed-loop with new atomic operators, (ii) incorporates a GAN approach for generating diverse and realistic test cases by learning patterns from both normal and abnormal network traffic, and (iii) employs LLMs to automate the generation of security testing rules.

The fuzzer uses server responses after each injection to guide a feedback-driven fuzzing loop that refines packet modifications in real time. By analyzing reactions, such as errors, state transitions or server-related metrics, NETWORKFUZZER adapts its strategy to better explore protocol behaviors and uncover hidden vulnerabilities. Furthermore, the GAN-based fuzzer enhances protocol testing by generating realistic packets that closely mimic valid traffic but with variations to expose edge-case vulnerabilities. It also leverages known DICOM attack patterns to craft malicious traffic, supporting both vulnerability discovery and the creation of synthetic datasets for training AI-based Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS) [18,19]. Finally, NETWORKFUZZER integrates LLMs to automate the generation of testing rules from protocol documentation, boosting both efficiency and accuracy while reducing manual effort.

Contributions. Our contributions are as follows.

- We design and implement NETWORKFUZZER, which is an open-source fuzzer for modifying and replaying any protocol network traffic using attack injection, fuzzing and generative AI.
- We evaluate the effectiveness of NETWORKFUZZER in real-world healthcare scenarios, demonstrating its ability to test DICOM servers and enhance network security testing.
- We construct a dataset containing DICOM traffic in pcap format to facilitate the analysis and testing of DICOM servers and security tools.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a background on the DICOM protocol and discusses relevant work in this research area. Next, Section 3 discusses the design of NETWORKFUZZER to address challenges

C1-C3. We then present the implementation and evaluate our tool in different scenarios for Section 4. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and offers insight into potential future directions for research and development.

2 Background & Related Work

We provide a brief overview of the DICOM protocol to understand the process of connection establishment, discuss related approaches for protocol testing, especially the network fuzzer 5GREPLAY, and then delve into our framework and its extensions in Section 3.

2.1 DICOM Protocol

The DICOM protocol is an application-layer standard designed for the exchange, storage, and retrieval of medical images, typically in the DICOM format. Operating over the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), DICOM ensures reliable and stateful communication between healthcare devices, such as PACS, imaging modalities, and workstations.

Fig. 1: DICOM basic communication protocol between a Calling AET (client) and a Called AET (server) with Association/Release, Error and Data Transfer packets.

associated, the Data Transfer phase begins, where the Calling AET transmits P-DATA packets containing DICOM payloads, such as medical images or metadata. Multiple P-DATA packets can be exchanged to support large datasets. Finally, in the Release phase, the Calling AET ends the session with an A-RELEASE-RQ packet, which the Called AET confirms with an A-RELEASE-RSP. For abrupt terminations, an A-ABORT packet may be sent.

DICOM Attacks. Some of the key threats [3,12] targeting DICOM communications and systems are as follows:

- *Man-in-the-Middle attack and packet manipulation:* Since traditional DICOM communication often lacks encryption, attackers can intercept, modify,

DICOM Communication. Figure 1 illustrates the DICOM communication protocol between a Calling Application Entity Title (AET) (client) and a Called AET (server), consisting of three main phases: Association, Data Transfer, and Release. In the Association phase, the Calling AET initiates the connection by sending an A-ASSOCIATE-RQ packet with parameters, such as Application Entity Titles, Presentation Contexts, and the list of supported services and transfer syntaxes. The Called AET responds with either A-ASSOCIATE-AC (Accept) to establish the connection or A-ASSOCIATE-RJ (Reject) if the request is invalid. Once associated, the Data Transfer phase begins, where the Calling AET transmits P-DATA

and inject malicious DICOM packets into the network. This enables them to alter attributes such as patient ID, study metadata, or image data, leading to data tampering, patient data exposure, unauthorized modifications, or incorrect medical diagnoses.

- *Replay attack*: Attackers can capture and replay previously recorded DICOM communications to a PACS server. This can result in duplicate image storage, incorrect medical records, or inconsistencies in patient management systems.
- *Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack*: By sending malformed DICOM packets or overwhelming the PACS server with excessive requests, attackers can degrade or completely disrupt medical imaging services, impacting hospital operations and patient care.
- *Malware hidden in DICOM files*: Since DICOM images support embedded metadata and private attributes, attackers can embed malware or other malicious payloads within DICOM files. If executed on a vulnerable system, this could lead to ransomware infections, data breaches, or system compromise.
- *Unauthorized access and weak authentication*: Many DICOM implementations rely on AETs for authentication, which can be easily guessed or spoofed. Without proper access controls, attackers can impersonate legitimate DICOM nodes to retrieve, modify, or delete medical images.

2.2 Related Work

Protocol Fuzzing. In general, there are approaches to fuzz and test network protocols, such as black-box fuzzing [6,14], symbolic execution [22] and grammar-based fuzzing [20]. Recently, ChatAFL [15] leverages pre-trained LLMs to perform grammar-aware mutations and predict the next input when fuzzing protocols to produce more effective inputs.

DICOM Testing. Wang et al. [23] addressed the security risks inherent in the implementation of the DICOM protocol by proposing a fuzzing-based vulnerability mining framework targeting open-source DICOM libraries. The authors developed a prototype system, DICOM-Fuzzer, featuring modules for test case generation, automated testing, and exception monitoring. Testing on the DCMTK library revealed a vulnerability causing buffer overflows with large input files, leading to DoS conditions in PACS systems.

Mirsky et al. [16] demonstrated how an attacker could exploit PACS servers by employing two conditional GAN models: one to inject false medical evidence into healthy images and another to remove evidence of tumors from diagnostic images. This method poses a significant threat as it could lead to misdiagnoses of serious medical conditions. High-resolution pathologies, which rely on precise imaging, are particularly vulnerable to such CTGAN-based attacks.

5GREPLAY. 5GREPLAY [21] is an open-source network fuzzer designed for fuzz testing 5G networks. It enables the evaluation of 5G components by replaying and modifying network traffic, as well as creating and injecting network scenarios into a target, which can be either a 5G core service or a Radio Access Network. Technically, 5GREPLAY can be viewed as a one-way bridge between NICs or can accept pre-captured packets saved in a PCAP-format file as input. The user

defines rules that explicitly specify which packets should pass through the bridge and how they should be modified. The configuration file also allows for specifying default actions for packets that do not match any rules, determining whether they should be forwarded or dropped. 5GREPLAY relies on MMT-DPI [4], which is a C library that implements Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) techniques to analyze network packets, classify the network protocol in use or the application a packet belongs to, and extract network and application-based events.

Fig. 2: 5GREPLAY global architecture [21].

For each incoming packet, 5GREPLAY classifies the packet to identify its protocol, extracts relevant protocol attributes used in the rules, and checks if any of the rules are satisfied. If no rules match, 5GREPLAY applies the default action as specified in the configuration file. The default action is either **FORWARD**, which sends the packet to the output NIC without modification, or **DROP**, which discards the packet. If the packet matches a rule, 5GREPLAY applies the action defined by the rule. If the action is **FORWARD**, the packet is modified according to the rule before being sent to the output NIC. 5GREPLAY currently supports several fundamental mutation operators for network traffic, including deleting or duplicating packets and modifying specific attributes in the headers of network packets.

We adopt and extend the 5GREPLAY to fuzz and test the DICOM protocol. Importantly, we address the limitations of the current fuzzer, as discussed in Section 1, to build a smart network fuzzer for DICOM targets.

3 NetworkFuzzer Design

In this section, we will present the architecture of NETWORKFUZZER and discuss how the design addresses the challenges **C1-C3** discussed in Section 1.

3.1 Architecture

Figure 3 presents an overview of NETWORKFUZZER and the fuzzing loop. Similar to traditional network traffic fuzzers, NETWORKFUZZER takes network traffic as input, either directly from a NIC or from pre-captured traffic in PCAP format, and performs various mutations on this traffic before sending it to the output NIC. Unlike existing network fuzzers like 5GREPLAY, where users manually create rules to modify traffic of interest and then manually observe the server’s reactions via logs after injecting the modified traffic, our smart fuzzer automates and enhances this process. Our fuzzer intelligently generates mutation rules and dynamically adapts its behavior based on real-time responses from the server

Fig. 3: Architecture of NETWORKFUZZER.

under test through a *closed-loop* fuzzing process. This adaptation is enabled by a Feedback Collector module, which monitors various forms of feedback such as server response packets, performance metrics under stress, and system behavior after receiving malformed or abnormal packets sent from the client. Specifically, our smart fuzzer, NETWORKFUZZER, integrates three key components to address the challenges **C1-C3**:

1. **Protocol Traffic Mutator** analyzes legitimate network traffic to extract protocol-specific attributes and applies mutation operators, such as delete, forward, duplicate, and reorder. By systematically modifying traffic, the mutator generates diverse test cases that simulate realistic and edge-case scenarios, addressing **C1** (*diversity in traffic generation*).
2. **GAN-based Traffic Generator** employs GANs to generate synthetic traffic samples to complement the deterministic mutations from the Protocol Traffic Mutator. By learning patterns from real network traffic, the GAN-based Generator creates realistic yet novel packet sequences, effectively addressing **C2** (*intelligent traffic synthesis*) and expanding the test coverage.
3. **LLM-based Rule Generator** leverages a LLM to generate testing rules dynamically based on protocol specifications, extracted attributes, and past testing results. The LLM-based Rule Generator ensures the fuzzer adapts to new protocols and scenarios, tackling **C3** (*adaptability and scalability*).

By leveraging automated analysis and feedback mechanisms, it ensures a more efficient, scalable, and thorough exploration of potential vulnerabilities, significantly reducing the need for manual intervention and increasing testing accuracy. In the next subsections, we will discuss the technical details of the three principal components.

3.2 Protocol Traffic Mutator

Protocol Analysis. Similar to 5GREPLAY, NETWORKFUZZER utilizes MMT-DPI [4], a C-based library that employs Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) techniques to analyze network traffic. MMT-DPI has a plugin architecture for easily adding new protocols and analysis techniques including machine learning techniques.

Leveraging its plugin-based architecture, which facilitates the addition of new protocols and analysis techniques, we developed a custom plugin for MMT-DPI to extract attributes specific to the DICOM protocol.

Figure 4 presents the attributes of DICOM packets extracted by the MMT-DPI library. These attributes include identifiers and metadata crucial for understanding and analyzing DICOM traffic. Specifically, attributes 1–15 correspond to the headers of DICOM packets, including fields such as Protocol Data Unit (PDU) type, Called or Calling AET, presentation context, etc, which are essential for decoding the structure and semantics of DICOM communications. The remaining attributes are general-purpose attributes applicable to all packets, providing valuable insights into the temporal and statistical characteristics of the traffic.

Once that key attributes are extracted through MMT-DPI, NETWORKFUZZER can use them for generating the attack traffic. By extracting these attributes, the plugin enables comprehensive analysis and manipulation of DICOM traffic, supporting use cases such as protocol evaluation, performance monitoring, and network testing. The modularity of MMT-DPI ensures that this extension integrates seamlessly with existing tools and workflows for DICOM traffic analysis.

Mutation Operators. The Protocol Traffic Mutator module processes incoming network traffic, applies different mutation operations, and optionally reorders packets before forwarding them to an output NIC. Initially, the algorithm loads a set of rules and a configuration file, which define the actions to be taken for different types of packets. A new buffer, as shown in Figure 3, is also initialized to temporarily store packets that are modified or forwarded for potential reordering. As packets are received, a packet processing algorithm similar to that of 5GREPLAY, is applied to modify them. Once all packets have been processed, the module optionally reorders the buffered packets by applying a random reorder operator, depending on the configuration. The use of a buffer, along with the additional reordering step, allows for random shuffling of multiple packets before they are injected into the network, providing greater flexibility and control over the traffic mutation process.

3.3 GAN-based Traffic Generator

This module focuses on the generation of synthetic DICOM network traffic by leveraging CTGAN [25]. The process consists of three main steps, as shown in

Protocol id 701	---	Name dicom
Attribute id 1	---	Name pdu_type
Attribute id 2	---	Name pdu_len
Attribute id 3	---	Name proto_version
Attribute id 4	---	Name called_ae_title
Attribute id 5	---	Name calling_ae_title
Attribute id 6	---	Name application_context
Attribute id 7	---	Name presentation_context
Attribute id 8	---	Name max_pdu_length
Attribute id 9	---	Name implementation_class_uid
Attribute id 10	---	Name pdv_length
Attribute id 11	---	Name pdv_context
Attribute id 12	---	Name pdv_flags
Attribute id 13	---	Name command_group_length
Attribute id 14	---	Name command_field
Attribute id 15	---	Name patient_name
Attribute id 4096	---	Name p_hdr
Attribute id 4097	---	Name p_data
Attribute id 4098	---	Name p_payload
Attribute id 4099	---	Name packet_count
Attribute id 4100	---	Name data_count
Attribute id 4101	---	Name payload_count
Attribute id 4102	---	Name first_packet_time
Attribute id 4103	---	Name last_packet_time
Attribute id 4104	---	Name p_data_len
Attribute id 4105	---	Name stats

Fig. 4: Key attributes of DICOM packets extracted by MMT-DPI.

Fig. 5: Architecture of GAN-based Traffic Generator module.

Figure 5: (i) processing and labeling DICOM flows from normal and abnormal PCAPs into structured CSV files, (ii) training a CTGAN model to generate synthetic DICOM-specific features while preserving key network identifiers, and (iii) modifying real PCAPs with synthetic values to create replayable traffic for testing DICOM servers.

Dataset Preprocessing. We first construct a dataset of legitimate and abnormal DICOM communications by capturing traffic in PCAP format. Each PCAP file was processed to extract flow-level features using a combination of standard and protocol-specific tools. Specifically, CICFlowMeter and Zeek were employed to extract general network flow statistics, such as flow duration, packet size, inter-arrival time, TCP flag counts, etc. Additionally, MMT-DPI and Wireshark were used to extract fine-grained DICOM-related attributes from packet headers, such as PDU type, PDU length, command field, etc. The extracted features were merged and aggregated into two CSV files: one containing normal DICOM flows and another containing abnormal ones, obtained through prior mutation and injection testing using NETWORKFUZZER. Non-DICOM flows were filtered out using port-based heuristics and application-layer protocol identification, ensuring only relevant traffic was retained. Each record was labeled accordingly: 0 for normal flows and 1 for abnormal ones. Specifically, the dataset contains 146 features, including 84 general features and 72 DICOM-related features.

Training the CTGAN. To enrich the dataset with realistic synthetic samples, we applied a CTGAN, which is particularly suited for generating structured tabular data with mixed data types and imbalanced class distributions, which are common in network traffic datasets. The GAN was trained using both normal and abnormal CSV datasets, learning conditional relationships between protocol-specific features. During generation, the model was constrained to preserve static fields, such as `src_ip`, `dst_ip`, `src_port`, `dst_port`, while allowing CTGAN to synthesize plausible values for the remaining DICOM-related fields. This ensures that generated flows remain consistent with real-world addressing while simulating novel variations in DICOM semantics. The synthetic flows produced by CTGAN were labeled based on the conditioning parameters used during generation (normal or abnormal) and exported as new CSV files for further processing.

Synthetic PCAP Generation. The final stage involves converting synthetic CSV flows into full PCAP files. This is accomplished by modifying real PCAPs using NETWORKFUZZER and Scapy, guided by synthetic values generated by CTGAN. Specifically, selected DICOM-related fields, such as command codes, message IDs, and dataset attributes, are rewritten to reflect the synthetic data, while preserving the original packet structure and timing. General static fields, such as source/destination IPs and ports, remain unchanged to facilitate con-

sistent testing. The resulting PCAPs represent a realistic blend of legitimate and synthetic traffic, suitable for replay and injection into testbed environments to assess DICOM server robustness. These PCAPs can also support anomaly detection and IDPS evaluations under diverse, high-fidelity traffic conditions.

3.4 LLM-based Rule Generator

To address the manual process of creating rules, especially for non-experts, we utilize LLMs to automate test rule generation.

Preprocessing Documentation. The first step of the LLM-based module involves understanding the DICOM protocol, its key attributes, and the valid and invalid values associated with them. To extract relevant information, we leverage advanced LLMs such as OpenAI GPT-4, which have been trained on extensive data from websites and technical documents. To evaluate its effectiveness, we test the model by asking a set of specific DICOM-related questions and manually verifying the responses using trusted resources [2], especially part 8 — DICOM network communication support for message exchange. Our observations indicate that LLM models are capable of interpreting the DICOM protocol specifications, performing reasoning and inference across multiple sections, and answering non-trivial questions about various DICOM attributes correctly.

Prompt Design. To ensure that the LLM-based rule generation module produces structured and syntactically correct XML rules for testing DICOM attributes, we design a well-defined prompt as shown below. The prompt below provides a clear instruction to the LLM, specifying its role as an expert in DICOM protocol testing and network fuzzing. It includes example rules, for example in Listing 1.1, to guide the model in generating similar rules based on user requests. The prompt emphasizes key aspects such as embedding meaningful comments within the generated C function, correctly setting the required attributes (e.g., `property_id`, `description`, and `if_satisfied`), and ensuring the appropriate use of helping functions (e.g., `replace_dicom_attribute()`), with protocol DICOM with ID 701 and the corresponding attribute ID. Additionally, the prompt enforces constraints on attribute selection by providing a predefined list of valid attributes, as shown in Section 3.2. If a user requests a rule for an unsupported attribute, the LLM is instructed to return a predefined error message.

Example prompt provided to the LLM

You are an expert in DICOM protocol testing and network fuzzing. Your task is to generate XML rules for testing DICOM attributes with valid or invalid values. Below are example rule structures: {EXAMPLE_RULE}.

There are two main types of rules you can generate:

1. Drop Rules: Use `#drop()` to drop specific DICOM packets [redacted]
2. Modification Rules: Use `replace_dicom_attribute()` to modify packet contents [redacted]

- Please generate a similar rule based on the user's request. The rule should:
1. Include proper embedded C function with meaningful comments
 2. Set appropriate `property_id`, `description`, and `if_satisfied` attributes
 3. Define correct `boolean_expression` based on the attribute being tested
 4. Use `replace_dicom_attribute()` with protocol ID 701 and the correct attribute ID
 5. Properly set `is_string` to 1 for string values and 0 for numeric values

IMPORTANT: You can ONLY use the following DICOM attributes: `{valid_attributes}`. If the user requests an attribute that is not in this list, respond with: "The requested attribute is not supported in the current DICOM implementation. Please choose from the list of supported attributes: `{valid_attributes}`".

Return ONLY the XML rule without any additional explanation if the attribute is supported, or ONLY the error message if it's not supported.

```
<beginning>
<!-- Property 32: Modify the PDU length to increase the payload size -->
<embedded_functions><![CDATA[
    static void em_modify_dicom_pdu_len(const rule_info_t *rule, int verdict
        , uint64_t timestamp, uint64_t counter, const mmt_array_t * const
        trace) {
        int is_string = 0;
        int new_val = 10000; // Set PDU length to 10000 bytes
        replace_dicom_attribute(701, 2, &new_val, is_string);
        forward_packet();
    }
]></embedded_functions>
<property property_id="32" type_property="FORWARD"
    description="Modify DICOM PDU length to invalid value (10000)"
    if_satisfied="em_modify_dicom_pdu_len">
    <event description="Got any DICOM packets"
        boolean_expression="((dicom.pdu_type > 0) &&& (dicom.
            pdu_type < 8))"/>
</property>
</beginning>
```

Listing 1.1: One of several example rules provided to the LLM

4 Implementation & Evaluation

4.1 Implementation

DICOM Simulator. We implement the DICOM simulator in Python using the *Pydicom* (version 2.4.4) and *Pynetdicom* (version 2.1.1) libraries. The simulator replicates legitimate DICOM communication functionalities, including establishing a connection, sending and retrieving DICOM files, and releasing the connection to a PACS server. Additionally, we account for all potential scenarios in which the server may return error responses, such as A-ASSOCIATE-RJ and A-ABORT. This comprehensive approach enables us to capture all possible cases of DICOM communication between the Calling and Called AET in PCAP format, forming a dataset of legitimate DICOM traffic for further analysis.

MMT-DPI Plugin for DICOM. We develop a new plugin for MMT-DPI to extract key attributes of the DICOM protocol. The plugin is tested against a dataset of legitimate PCAP files captured on the server after executing the DICOM simulator. The extracted values are verified by cross-checking with the DICOM communication documentation and validating them using other packet analysis tools, such as Wireshark.

NETWORKFUZZER. NETWORKFUZZER extends 5GREPLAY (version 0.0.8, commit 86f2074) by integrating new mutation operators, a GAN-based Traffic Generator, and a LLM-based Rule Generator. The GAN-based Traffic Generator utilizes CTGAN (version 0.11.0) to generate synthetic traffic. While the LLM-based Rule Generator employs a GPT-4 model for learning and generating mutation rules, it can also use open-source LLM models such as LLaMA 2 or Mistral.

4.2 Experimental Setup

Attack Modeling. We consider the threat model for an attacker targeting a DICOM system within an internal network. We assume that the attacker has gained unauthorized access to the internal network, either through an insider threat, or by exploiting a vulnerability in another networked device. With this level of access, the attacker can conduct reconnaissance, intercept DICOM communications, and launch targeted attacks against the PACS server and connected devices. Additionally, we assume that the DICOM server lacks certain security enhancements and is misconfigured, making it vulnerable to attacks that could compromise data integrity, confidentiality, and availability.

Testbed Setup. Figure 6 illustrates the simulated environment used to evaluate the capabilities of NETWORKFUZZER in different DICOM protocol testing scenarios, as discussed below in this section. The testbed consists of three key components: a client machine, a server machine, and a traffic capturing and analysis framework. The client machine is an Ubuntu Virtual Machine (VM) (version 22.04) running the DICOM simulation, where NETWORKFUZZER is installed and executed to generate and inject test traffic, including potential attack scenarios. On the HES

Fig. 6: The DICOM testbed.

premise, the server machine is another Ubuntu VM (version 22.04) hosting Orthanc [5], a free and open-source lightweight DICOM server deployed as a service to process and respond to DICOM requests. Additionally, the MMT security monitoring framework is installed on the server machine for packet sniffing and analysis. Furthermore, we utilize additional open-source tools, such as tcpdump and Wireshark, on the server machine to capture and analyze network traffic, complementing the MMT framework.

Research Questions. In this section, we conduct experiments to evaluate effectiveness of NETWORKFUZZER in testing the DICOM protocol. These experiments aim to answer the following research questions: (i) efficiency and reliability of LLM-based Rule Generator (Section 4.3); (ii) real attack scenario performed by NETWORKFUZZER (Section 4.4); and (iii) effectiveness of GAN-based approach in synthetic traffic generation (Section 4.5).

4.3 RQ1: Efficiency and Reliability of LLM-based Rule Generator

To assess the effectiveness of the LLM-based rule generator, we conducted an evaluation focusing on correctness, execution feasibility, and its impact on security testing efficiency. By employing this module, we automatically generated 40 test rules, each designed to either drop specific DICOM packets or modify specific DICOM attributes using valid or invalid values. All generated rules conformed to the expected XML structure. Furthermore, the rules were compiled and executed by our fuzzer without requiring manual corrections, enabling direct manipulation of corresponding attributes in real DICOM network traffic.

```

Generating rule for: "Make a rule that sends invalid protocol version of DICOM packets A-ASSOCIATE-RQ"
Generated Rule (Property ID: 107):
-----
<beginning>
<!-- Property 107: Modify the protocol version to an invalid value -->
<embedded_functions><[[CDATA[
static void em_modify_dicom_proto_version(
    const rule_info_t *rule, int verdict, uint64_t timestamp,
    uint64_t counter, const mmt_array_t * const trace) {
    int is_string = 0;
    int new_val = 9999; // Set protocol version to an invalid value
    // Replace protocol version field (attribute ID 3 in protocol 701)
    replace_dicom_attribute(701, 3, &new_val, is_string);
    forward_packet();
}
]]></embedded_functions>
<property property_id="107" type_property="FORWARD"
description="Modify DICOM protocol version to invalid value (9999)"
if_satisfied="em_modify_dicom_proto_version">
<event description="Got A-ASSOCIATE-RQ DICOM packets"
bool_expr="!(dicom_pdu_type == 1) &amp;&amp; (dicom_proto_version != 9999)"/>
</property>
</beginning>
-----
Rule saved to: rules/dicom_rule_modify_dicom_protocol_version_to_invalid_value_9999.xml
Property ID: 107 (automatically assigned to avoid conflicts)
You can now use 'networkfuzzer compile' to compile the rule.

```

Fig. 7: Example of a rule generated by our module based on the user’s request.

This automation significantly reduced the time and effort required by security engineers. To validate the accuracy of the generated rules, we executed our fuzzer with these rules and captured the modified PCAP files for verification using the MMT-DPI and external tools such as Wireshark. The results demonstrated that the automated approach consistently produced functionally equivalent rules while maintaining adherence to DICOM protocol specifications, thereby facilitating the testing of DICOM implementations. Furthermore, generating all potential rules using our module takes approximately 131 seconds in total and costs \$0.37, demonstrating its great efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

This experiment highlights the efficiency and reliability of our LLM-based approach, demonstrating its potential to enhance automated security testing of network protocols in general, and the DICOM protocol in particular.

4.4 RQ2: Real DICOM Extraction Attack Scenario

The DICOM Extraction Attack is a real multi-phase intrusion scenario targeting medical imaging servers like Orthanc through the DICOM protocol, aiming to

Fig. 8: DICOM extraction attack.

silently extract sensitive patient data and images. The scenario contains five main steps, as depicted in Figure 8. The attack begins with step 1 Discovery, where the attacker scans the network using tools like nmap to identify active DICOM endpoints on port 4242. Once a server is located, the attacker initiates step 2 Called AET Brute-Force, where our NETWORKFUZZER is used to attempt different Called AET values through repeated A-ASSOCIATE-RQ packets. Once a valid Called AET is found and a session is established, the attack proceeds to step 3 Patient Metadata Enumeration, where NETWORKFUZZER issues crafted C-FIND queries to the Orthanc server to retrieve indexed patient data. Responses from the server expose sensitive metadata including patient names, study dates, and unique identifiers such as `StudyInstanceUID`. These identifiers become the foundation for step 4 DICOM File Extraction, where the attacker sends C-MOVE requests to download actual DICOM images associated with selected patients. Finally, in step 5 Optional Analysis, the attacker may locally analyze, modify, or exfiltrate the collected DICOM files for malicious purposes, such as patient data leaks, tampering with diagnostics, or insurance fraud.

(a) Fuzzing packets in step 2 (b) Fuzzing packets in step 3

Fig. 9: Packets captured on the DICOM server during the attack.

The two most critical steps in this sequence are step 2 and step 3, which are not intended to crash the server, but rather to extract sensitive medical metadata that can later be exploited. Using closed-loop fuzzing, NETWORKFUZZER dynamically adapts its inputs based on server feedback, fine-tuning its behavior through *on-the-fly rule generation*, thanks to rules produced by the LLM-based Rule Generator module, in order to gather the maximum amount of information. In step 2, rather than sending random values, NETWORKFUZZER iterates over plausible Called AET candidates (e.g., ‘ORTHANC’, ‘PACS’, ‘IMAGING’, etc.), constructing minimal but valid A-ASSOCIATE-RQ packets. Figure 9a shows the fuzzing packets sent by NETWORKFUZZER to the DICOM server. For each trial, it observes the server’s response, if A-ASSOCIATE-ACCEPT indicates a valid Called AET, while a rejection or no response leads to refinement.

In Step 3, NETWORKFUZZER exploits the DICOM C-FIND service to query indexed patient information stored on the server. Since the server enforces restrictions that prevent the use of the wildcard character ‘*’ to retrieve all patient records, only the single-character wildcard ‘?’ is allowed. To work around this limitation, NETWORKFUZZER begins by fuzzing the PatientName field incrementally, starting with ‘?’, then ‘??’, and so on, to infer the length of valid patient names. Once the approximate length is determined, it proceeds to brute-force the initial characters (e.g., for length 5: ‘A????’, ‘B????’, etc.), analyzing the length of server responses to identify valid entries. A response packet with a total size of 154 bytes containing 100 bytes of DICOM payload indicates that no results were found, while longer responses suggest the presence of valid patient data. Through closed-loop fuzzing, NETWORKFUZZER dynamically refines its queries, specifically adjusting the patient name values in rules, to efficiently extract metadata, as shown in Figure 9b.

This real scenario demonstrates how an attacker can exploit weaknesses in DICOM implementations through a feedback-driven process using our NETWORKFUZZER. By leveraging closed-loop fuzzing, NETWORKFUZZER modifies packets and injects them in real time based on server responses, using on-the-fly rule generation to maximize data extraction.

4.5 RQ3: Effectiveness of GAN-based Module

To evaluate the quality of synthetic PCAP files generated by our GAN-based module, we adopted a *post-hoc replacement* approach in which all DICOM-related features were replaced with synthetic values generated by CTGAN. We applied a set of statistical metrics to assess the similarity between original and synthetic datasets, grouped by feature type:

- Total Variation Distance (TVD): Measures the difference between the original and synthetic categorical distributions.
- Chi2 p-value: Assesses whether the observed categorical distribution is statistically different from the expected distribution.
- Category Coverage (CatCov): Evaluates the diversity of categories in the synthetic data compared to the original.
- Discrete Kullback-Leibler Divergence (D-KLD): Quantifies the divergence between the original and synthetic categorical distributions.
- Integrated Kullback-Leibler Similarity (IKS): Measures the similarity between the original and synthetic continuous feature distributions.
- Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC): Assesses the linear correlation between the continuous features in the synthetic and original datasets.
- Statistical Similarity (StatSimilarity): Measures the overall statistical similarity between the continuous feature distributions.
- Continuous Kullback-Leibler Divergence (C-KLD): Quantifies the divergence between the original and synthetic continuous feature distributions.

The results in Table 1 indicate that the GAN-based module performs effectively in modeling continuous DICOM features. High values of *IKS* (0.9847), *StatSimilarity* (0.9925), and *C-KLD* (0.9793) demonstrate strong similarity between synthetic and original distributions for continuous features. For discrete features, although some divergence is observed, the high *Chi2 p-value* suggests that these differences are not statistically significant. The *Category Coverage* (0.3936) reveals limited diversity in categorical values, suggesting room for improvement in capturing rare categories. However, during injection of synthetic PCAPs generated by modifying multiple values using CTGAN, we observed warnings and errors in the DICOM server logs, suggesting potential structural inconsistencies or invalid field lengths. This highlights the need for tighter protocol-conformant constraints during generation, which we plan to address in future work.

Feature	Mean Value
Discrete Features	
TVD	0.6076
Chi2_pvalue	0.8042
CatCov	0.3936
D-KLD	0.4187
Continuous Features	
IKS	0.9847
PCC	0.0188
StatSimilarity	0.9925
C-KLD	0.9793

Table 1: Summary of evaluation metrics (mean values) for synthetic DICOM data

The CTGAN model is effective at generating realistic synthetic data for both categorical and continuous features but had limitations in preserving the full diversity of categories in discrete features. The GAN-based module shows potential for augmenting protocol-level datasets in cybersecurity and DICOM analysis.

5 Conclusion & Future Work

In this paper, we design and implement a network fuzzer, NETWORKFUZZER, to test network protocols, with a focus on the DICOM protocol in the healthcare domain. NETWORKFUZZER is built on top of the existing open-source fuzzer 5GREPLAY, but has been extended to enhance traffic diversity, enable intelligent generation, and improve adaptability for a broader range of protocols. We employ NETWORKFUZZER to execute real attack scenarios against a DICOM server, aiming to extract patient metadata and simulate further malicious actions. This demonstrates NETWORKFUZZER’s ability to modify traffic dynamically, generate rules on the fly based on server responses, and produce synthetic malicious traffic.

In the future, we plan to extend the network fuzzer to make it more generic for testing additional protocols, particularly those used in 5G and 6G networks. Enhancing NETWORKFUZZER, especially by integrating LLMs into MMT-DPI plugins to automatically extract attributes from new protocols, will significantly reduce the manual effort required when dealing with unfamiliar protocol structures. We also plan to integrate the fuzzer with AI4SOAR [19] to simulate and evaluate real-time mitigation strategies against protocol-specific attacks.

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